

COMPETENCIES AND PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS IN BALO-I DISTRICT

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Competencies and Performance of Teachers in Balo-I District

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Abstract

The study is a descriptive-correlation research design. This study assessed the teaching competencies and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings of educators in the public schools situated in the Balo-I District of Lanao del Norte, Philippines. Employing a descriptive-correlation research design, the study used descriptive research methods to elucidate the socio-economic profile, including age, sex, length of service, number of training sessions attended, and teacher position. The study's participants were the teachers from the Balo-I District within the Division of Lanao Del Norte, SY 2022–2023. Result of the evaluation of teachers' competencies and performance offers a favourable perspective on the overall educational landscape. The robust competencies demonstrated in knowledge, skills, and attitudes underscore a commitment to effective teaching practices, fostering a student-centered learning environment. The emphasis on real-life examples, effective communication, and continuous professional development reflects a dynamic teaching approach that contributes to a positive and engaging educational atmosphere.

Keywords: *competencies, performance, teachers, district, research*

Introduction

Department of Education adopted the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) as a quality assurance tool in implementing the K to 12 Curriculum. The domains of the PPST comprise the complete competency that guarantees the manifestation of the best teaching practices globally. The Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 019, s. 2022, which will serve as a guide in the selection, hiring, appointment, and promotion of individuals in the teaching, school administration, related teaching, and non-teaching positions in all Department of Education offices and schools.

The Department of Education (DepEd) underscored the new importance of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) that is aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in ensuring the delivery of quality, accessible, relevant, and liberating primary education in the country. Through this, teachers are expected to apply mastery of content knowledge and its application across learning areas. They must facilitate learning using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies and classroom management practices. They must manage an environment conducive to learning and address learning diversity (Batuigas, 2022).

Geared towards competency-based performance management, professional development, and career progression, the PPST-based RPMS for teachers shall utilize all 37 indicators of the PPST and shall be distributed across three school years (SYs): 2022-2023, SY 2023-2024, and SY 2024-2025. DepEd Memorandum titled Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) details the enclosed procedures and all the other necessary information on the adoption and implementation of performance management and appraisal of teachers (DepEd, 2023).

Based on the data in many places worldwide, teacher competency has surfaced as a critical concern, and 60 million teachers globally require career development to develop their teaching skills. Half of the teachers in developing nations were unprepared compared to their country's stated teacher education criteria (Mahmoud, 2023).

According to Philippine data, 60 million teachers globally require career development to develop their teaching skills among the types of teacher competencies and performance in Balo-I District. The PPST-based RPMS for teachers shall utilize all 37 PPST indicators and be distributed across three school years (SYs): 2022-2023, SY 2023-2024, and SY 2024-2025. DepEd Memorandum titled Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST). Furthermore, Balo-I district remain a problem for challenging in hurdles in accomplishing and meeting the necessary outputs in every objective considering the daily routine or task of teachers.

Moreover, the study is conducted to determine the competencies and performance of teachers in the Balo-I District. The research was conducted this school year 2023-2024. Also, the researcher is a grade four teacher for three years in the locale of study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the teachers' competencies based on their IPCRF rating in the public schools in Balo-I District, Lanao del Norte, Philippines, for the SY 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of,
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;

- 1.3 length of service;
- 1.4 numbers of training attended; and
- 1.5 teachers' plantilla position?
2. What is the level of teacher's competencies in terms of:
 - 2.1 knowledge;
 - 2.2 skills; and
 - 2.3 attitudes?
3. What is the teachers' performance of the respondents based on the IPCRF rating?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of teachers' competencies and their IPCRF rating?
5. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods used in the study. It discussed the research design, research environment, respondents and sampling procedures, research instruments and their validity, data gathering procedures, and statistical data treatment.

Research Design

The study used the descriptive-correlation research design. The study was descriptive since it described the socio-economic profile in terms of age, sex, length of service, number of training sessions attended and teacher's position. Likewise, the respondents' socio-demographic profile and the teachers' competencies were correlated to the performance of the respondents.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the Balo-i District teachers, Division of Lanao Del Norte, during the school year 2022-2023. The researchers utilized random sampling in choosing the respondents in the study from the schools of Balo-i District. A summary of the distribution of respondents by school level is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Number of teachers per school*

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Balo-I Central Elementary School	1	48	49
Maria Cristina Central Elementary School	0	21	21
Abaga Integrated School	1	13	14
Cadayonan Integrated School	0	16	16
Total	2	98	100

Instruments

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire based from DepEd Memorandum No. 008 s. 2023 Multi- Year Guidelines on the Result Based Performance Management System- Philippines Professional Standards for Teachers. The questionnaire is divided into two parts: the first is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, number of training attended, plantilla position and the second questionnaire has three parts. The first part is composed of 10 questions about the teachers' competence in terms of knowledge. Part 2 of the survey questionnaire consists of 10 questions about the teachers' competence in terms of skills. The last part has 10 questions about the teachers' competence in terms of attitude.

To ensure the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire underwent a pilot testing at Pacalundo Integrated School. The reliability statistics result showed Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the study variables. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency, which indicates how well the items in a scale or questionnaire are measuring the same construct. In general, Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7 are considered reliable, and values above 0.9 are excellent. Based on this criterion, the study variable in the study is considered reliable, with Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7. Thus, the instrument used in this study has at least acceptable internal consistency, indicating that it can be used for future research purposes.

Reliability Statistics Result

<i>Study Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>	<i>Description</i>
Knowledge level	.721	10	Acceptable
Skills level	.814	10	Good
Attitude level	.812	10	Good

Note: Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 is considered reliable

LEGENDS: (George & Mallery, 2003)

≥ 0.90	Excellent
0.80-0.89	Good
0.70-0.79	Acceptable
0.60-0.69	Questionable
0.50-0.59	Poor
≤ 0.49	Unacceptable

Procedure

The data were gathered in the following procedure, the permission to conduct the study was obtained, and all communications will be signed and approved by the Adviser, and the Dean of the Graduate Studies of St. Peter's College addressed to Lanao Del Norte Division Superintendent. After receiving consent, the researcher administered the survey questionnaires to the respondents during their vacant time. The researcher discussed and explained the vital parts and mechanics of how to answer some parts of it. The questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first is the profile of the respondents and the second questionnaire has three parts. It's about the teachers' competence in terms of their knowledge, skill and attitude. The respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaire and it was then retrieved after the respondents are done answering the questionnaire. The confidentiality of their answers was guaranteed by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems. For problem 1- Frequency and Percentage were used in analyzing the profile of the respondents as to age, sex, length of service, number of training attended and teacher position and the teaching performance of teachers. For problems 2 and 3 - Mean and Standard deviations were used to determine the focus of the respondents in terms of teaching competencies based on the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of teachers from Balo-I District as well as the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF rating. For problems 4 & 5- ANOVA was used to illustrate the relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the teaching performance, and the significant relationship between the teaching competencies and the teaching performance of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, and discussion of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, numbers of trainings attended and teachers' plantilla position?

Table 1. Age

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-29	11	11.0
30-39	36	36.0
40-49	32	32.0
50-59	21	21.0
Total	100	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 40.53 (9.15)

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age in a research study. The majority of respondents fall within the age range of 30-39, constituting 36% of the total sample. Following closely, the 40-49 age group represents 32%, while the 20-29 and 50-59 age groups account for 11% and 21% of the respondents, respectively. The total sample size is 100 individuals, with an overall mean age of 40.53 years and a standard deviation (SD) of 9.15. The data suggest a relatively balanced representation of various age groups in the study, with a slight inclination towards middle-aged participants. The majority of respondents answered in the age range with 30-3, constituting 32%. Accordingly, to the studies showed with this, the 21st-century teacher should employ strategies with high consideration to non-restricted age, sex or distance. It should consider accessible and affordable education where technology should use as a tool and an advantage for acquiring knowledge and skills (Mangonon, 2021).

Table 2. Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	2	2.0
Female	98	98.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 shows the gender distribution among the respondents in the research study. The overwhelming majority of participants identify as female, constituting 98% of the total sample. In contrast, males represent a significantly smaller portion, making up only 2% of the respondents. The result implied that in the Department of Education, there were more female employed than male.

Table 3. Years of Service

Years of Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below-5	15	15.0
6-10	21	21.0
11-15	25	25.0
16-20	16	16.0
21-above	23	23.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 provides a breakdown of the respondents' years of service in the research study. The largest proportion of participants, 25%,

falls within the 11-15 years of service category, followed closely by the 21-above years of service category, which accounts for 23% of the total sample. The 6-10 and 21-above years of service groups each represent 21%, while the below-5 and 16-20 years of service groups make up 15% and 16%, respectively. The data suggested a relatively even distribution of participants across different tenure brackets, providing a diverse representation of the workforce in terms of experience. According to Boyd et al., (2010) claimed that improvement occurs over the first 4 or 5 years, but point out that this is an average, and some less experienced teachers improve much more quickly than others. Many of the studies that found student achievement was influenced by teachers' years of experience identified these effects only in the first 3 years of a teacher's career: The average teacher is at his or her worst during the first year in the classroom, gets better in the second year, a little better in the third year, and then never gets any better after that. (Jacob, 2012).

Table 4. *Number of Training Attended*

<i>Number of Training Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
0-2	58	58.0
3-4	19	19.0
5-6	10	10.0
7-above	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 outlines the distribution of respondents based on the number of training sessions attended in the research study. The majority of participants, constituting 58%, have attended between 0 and 2 training sessions. Following this, the 3-4 training sessions category represents 19% of the total sample, while the 5-6 training sessions and 7-above training sessions categories account for 10% and 13%, respectively. The data indicated a spectrum of engagement in training activities among the respondents, with a substantial portion having limited exposure to training sessions. In line with the goal of promoting quality education, it is also imperative to upgrade the quality of teachers we have. Professional standards, training, and advancement are all related to the quality and professionalism of teachers. As a result, teacher preparation is critical in both training and setting the groundwork for their professional growth (Panda, 2019).

Table 5. *Teaching Position*

<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	63	63.0
Teacher II	16	16.0
Teacher III	12	12.0
Master Teacher I	7	7.0
Master Teacher II	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 details the distribution of respondents based on their teaching positions. The majority of participants, comprising 63%, hold the position of Teacher I, indicating a substantial representation of entry-level teaching roles in the study. Teacher II represents 16%, Teacher III accounts for 12%, and Master Teacher I and Master Teacher II contribute 7% and 2%, respectively, to the total sample. This breakdown provides valuable insights into the hierarchical structure of the teaching staff, emphasizing a predominant presence of individuals in early career stages. The data on teaching positions are essential for understanding the composition of the educator workforce, which can have implications for professional growth opportunities, mentorship programs, and strategies for improving overall teaching quality within educational institutions. In this study, Mondejar et al. (2022) it was stated that in terms of promotion, the majority of respondents agreed that seniority is given precedence in promotion choices and that job promotions are fair and equal. There is, however, no explicit promotion policy.

Moreover, they were unconvinced that promotion selections are based on merit and fitness. According to Pagayanan (2023), in promoting teachers from teacher 1 to teacher 3 or even up to master teacher 3, it was observed that the subject expertise of teachers is not tested thoroughly. Jumping from teacher 1 to teacher 3 requires a teacher to be more expert on his subject matter and fully equipped with all the competencies needed. This can only be done by a paper and pencil test to candidate teachers for promotion. Levelling of teachers can be fully justified if one knows that he passed a subject matter test. This should be much heavier if a teacher wanted to become a master teacher (NHS, 2023).

Problem 2: What is the level of teacher's competencies in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes?

Table 6. *Level of Teachers' Teaching Competencies in terms of Knowledge*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	3.50	0.54	Strongly Agree
2. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching context.	3.40	0.53	Agree
3. Design, select, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent which curriculum requirements.	3.45	0.52	Agree
4. Develops an appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	3.39	0.60	Agree
5. Answer student questions and provide explanations.	3.60	0.57	Strongly Agree

6. Incorporate critical thinking and problem-solving activities into the lessons.	3.34	0.57	Agree
7. Integrates real-life examples and applications into the lessons.	3.64	0.50	Strongly Agree
8. Demonstrate up-to-date knowledge in every learning area develop.	3.49	0.58	Agree
9. Explain difficult topics in a way that students can understand:	3.54	0.56	Strongly Agree
10. Full understanding of the subject matter.	3.55	0.61	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.49	0.37	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 6 presents the results of assessing teachers' teaching competencies in terms of knowledge, using various indicators with corresponding mean and standard deviation (SD) scores. The highest mean score is attributed to the indicator "Integrates real-life examples and applications into the lessons" with a mean of 3.64, indicating a strongly agree response. Other indicators such as "Answer student questions and provide explanations" (mean = 3.60), "Full understanding of the subject matter" (mean = 3.55), and "Explain difficult topics in a way that students can understand" (mean = 3.54) also received high mean scores, falling within the strongly agree category. The overall mean for all indicators is 3.49, placing it in the agreed category. Teachers' competencies are defined as dynamic and complex dimensions that combine attitudes, skills, and knowledge that lead to effective action in the real world (Chong & Cheah, 2009; O'Flaherty & Beal, 2018).

These results suggest a generally positive assessment of teachers' knowledge-related competencies. However, it is essential to note areas for potential improvements, such as the indicator "Incorporate critical thinking and problem-solving activities into the lessons," which received a slightly lower mean of 3.34 but still falls within the agreed category. Produce quality and professional educators. The ability of teachers to translate strategies, integrate knowledge and skills through reflective practice had been a significant turning point for the successful implementation of 21st century skills practices. Other studies prove that competent teachers are the ones who benefit their students. High teacher competence not only takes place in the classroom but also engages in the implementation of co-curricular activities (Dalapo, 2020).

Implications of these findings include the recognition of strengths in real-life application and explanation skills, but educators may benefit from targeted professional development to enhance critical thinking incorporation into lessons. Overall, these results offer valuable insights for educational institutions aiming to refine teaching competencies through tailored training programs and continuous professional development initiatives.

Table 7. Level of Teachers' Competencies in terms of Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher order thinking skill.	3.43	0.52	Agree
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	3.43	0.52	Agree
3. Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities a range of physical learning environment.	3.42	0.54	Agree
4. Manage learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	3.47	0.56	Agree
5. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strength, interest and experience.	3.45	0.56	Agree
6. Integrates numeracy and literacy skills in the lesson.	3.68	0.51	Strongly Agree
7. The ability to effectively communicate with students.	3.60	0.53	Strongly Agree
8. Competence in using educational technology tools and resources.	3.43	0.57	Agree
9. The teacher collaborates with colleagues and shares best practices to improve teaching and learning.	3.49	0.54	Agree
10. Continuous professional development and learning.	3.61	0.51	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.50	0.38	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 7 provides an assessment of teachers' teaching competencies in terms of skills, revealing positive mean scores across various indicators. The highest mean score is observed for the indicator "Integrates numeracy and literacy skills in the lesson" with a mean of 3.68, placing it in the strongly agree category. Similarly, indicators such as "The ability to effectively communicate with students" (mean = 3.60) and "Continuous professional development and learning" (mean = 3.61) also garnered high mean scores, falling within the strongly agree category. The overall mean for all indicators is 3.50, positioning it in the strongly agree category, indicating a high level of agreement with the assessed skills-related competencies. According to the educational literature, a competent teacher is qualified to fulfil his function as a consequence of understanding the skills, concepts, and tendencies inherent in competencies, and therefore the actual execution of the role he is qualified to play. (Adăscăliței et al., 2020).

The findings suggested that teachers demonstrate commendable skills in areas such as communication, collaboration, and the integration of technology into their teaching practices. The emphasis on continuous professional development and the sharing of best practices indicates a commitment to ongoing improvement. The positive assessment of skills-related competencies has implications for reinforcing these strengths in teacher training programs and encouraging a culture of collaboration and professional growth within

the educational institution. However, it is essential for educators and administrators to remain vigilant in addressing any potential gaps or areas for improvement that may emerge over time, ensuring a sustained high level of teaching competence.

Table 8. *Level of Teachers' Competencies in terms of Attitude*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. The teacher likes to establish a positive and inclusive classroom environment.	3.62	0.51	Strongly Agree
2. The teacher likes to encourage creativity and innovation among students.	3.58	0.52	Strongly Agree
3. The teacher feels motivated and inspires students to achieve their best.	3.62	0.51	Strongly Agree
4. The teacher likes to use hands-on learning activities with the learners.	3.57	0.59	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher loves to give group activities for the learners.	3.49	0.58	Agree
6. The teacher loves to respect and values the diverse backgrounds of students	3.68	0.49	Strongly Agree
7. The teacher loves to maintain professionalism and ethical conduct.	3.69	0.49	Strongly Agree
8. The teacher likes to open feedback and willing to improve.	3.66	0.50	Strongly Agree
9. The teacher loves to empathize and understand students' individual differences.	3.60	0.59	Strongly Agree
10. The teacher loves being approachable and open to suggestions for improvement.	3.66	0.52	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.62	0.39	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 8 reveals teachers' teaching competencies in terms of attitude, portraying positive mean scores across various indicators. Notably, several indicators received the highest mean score of 3.68, placing them in the strongly agree category. These include "The teacher loves to respect and value the diverse backgrounds of students," "The teacher loves to maintain professionalism and ethical conduct," and "The teacher loves to empathize and understand students' individual differences." Overall, the total measure yields a mean score of 3.62, categorizing it as strongly agree. Though studies indicate that supervision helps teachers to develop their teaching skills, it is still arguable whether teachers can improve their teaching performance in classroom. Thus, this study attempts to address the impact of supervision on teachers' performance and attitude (Enamul,2020).

The findings underscored a positive and inclusive attitude among teachers, emphasizing the creation of a supportive and encouraging classroom environment. Teachers express a strong commitment to fostering creativity, motivating students, and embracing diversity. The high mean scores in professionalism, openness to feedback, and willingness to improve suggest a culture of continuous self-reflection and growth. These positive attitudes are pivotal for creating an optimal learning environment and facilitating positive student-teacher relationships.

Implications of these results included the affirmation of educators' positive attitudes, which can serve as a foundation for promoting a conducive learning atmosphere. Educational institutions may capitalize on these strengths by reinforcing them in professional development programs and recognizing and celebrating teachers who exemplify these positive attitudes. Additionally, fostering a culture of openness to feedback and improvement can contribute to sustained excellence in teaching practices.

Table 9. *Consolidated Findings of the Level of Teachers' Teaching Competencies*

Teaching Competencies	Mean	SD	Description
Knowledge	3.49	0.37	Agree
Skills	3.50	0.38	Strongly Agree
Attitudes	3.62	0.39	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.54	0.34	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 9 provides a consolidated overview of the teachers' teaching competencies, combining assessments of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The mean scores for each competency category are 3.49 for knowledge (categorized as agree), 3.50 for skills (categorized as strongly agree), and 3.62 for attitudes (categorized as strongly agree). The overall total measure yields a mean score of 3.54, placing it in the strongly agree category. According to Zhao et al., (2020) asserts that the competencies that must be possessed by teachers include 1) pedagogic competencies, namely the ability to manage the learning, 2) personality competencies, namely personal abilities that are steady, stable, mature, wise and authoritative to be the role models for students. 3) competencies professional competence, namely the ability to master learning materials broadly and deeply, and 4) social competencies, namely the ability of teacher as part of community to communicate and socialize effectively.

These consolidated findings indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding teachers' competencies across knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Teachers demonstrated strength in their knowledge-related competencies, showcasing competence in content application, curriculum planning, and assessment strategies. The strong agreement in skills-related competencies emphasizes proficiency in teaching strategies, classroom management, and technology integration. Additionally, the strongly agree rating for attitudes underscores positive teacher dispositions, including a commitment to inclusivity, motivation, professionalism, and continuous improvement.

The implications of these consolidated findings are significant, suggesting a well-rounded and highly competent teaching force. Educational institutions can leverage these strengths to inform professional development initiatives, mentorship programs, and recruitment strategies. Recognizing and reinforcing positive attitudes and skills in the teaching staff can contribute to a positive and

effective learning environment, ultimately benefiting both educators and students.

Problem 3: What is the teaching performance of teachers based on IPCRF rating?

Table 10. Teaching Performance of the Teachers Based on IPCRF Rating

Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	0	0.0	Outstanding	Exceptional Performance
3.50-4.49	90	90.0	Very Satisfactory	High Performance
2.50-3.49	10	10.0	Satisfactory	Acceptable Performance
1.50-2.49	0	0.0	Unsatisfactory	Low Performance
1.00-1.49	0	0.0	Poor	Very Low
Total	100	100.0		

Note: Mean (SD) = 3.99 (.31)

Table 10 provides an overview of the teaching performance of the teachers based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings. The distribution reveals that the majority of teachers, 90%, fall within the range of 3.50-4.49, corresponding to a rating of "Very Satisfactory," indicating high performance. No teachers are rated as "Outstanding" (4.50-5.00) or "Unsatisfactory" (1.50-2.49), and the mean performance rating for the entire sample is 3.99, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.31. Teachers' teaching performance referred to the total of a teacher's efforts, abilities and perceptions about his or her teaching work both inside and outside the classroom (Wijayanti et al., 2020). According of Weisberg et al. noted that even when evaluation scales are broader and have multiple rating categories, 94% of teachers are given one of the top-two ratings. A second examination of teacher evaluation systems by Kraft and Gilmour (2017) found that although most states had modified their teacher evaluation systems, the percentage of teachers rated satisfactory remained at 99%.

These findings suggested a predominantly high level of teaching performance among the surveyed teachers. The fact that no teachers received the lowest or highest ratings indicates a concentration of performance in the middle ranges. The mean rating of 3.99 further supports the overall very satisfactory performance, reinforcing the idea of a well-performing teaching staff.

Implications of these results included the affirmation of the effectiveness of teaching practices within the educational institution. However, it is crucial for administrators and educators to analyze the specific components of the IPCRF ratings to identify areas of strength and areas for improvement. This data can guide targeted professional development initiatives and mentorship programs to sustain and enhance the high level of teaching performance observed. The absence of teachers in the outstanding or unsatisfactory categories suggests a generally consistent and balanced teaching quality across the surveyed population.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the teaching performance of the respondents?

Table 11. Regression Analysis of Relating the Demographic Profile and the Teaching Performance of the Respondents

Predictor	Regression Coeff.	S.E.	Stand. Coeff.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Gender (Female)	-.13	.24	-.43	-.55	.581	Not significant
Age	-.002	.006	-.05	-.28	.771	Not significant
Years of Service						
≤5	Ref.	--	--	--	--	--
6-10	-.01	.12	-.03	-.08	.931	Not significant
11-15	.09	.14	.28	.62	.520	Not significant
16-20	-.07	.17	-.24	-.45	.654	Not significant
21-above	-.06	.19	-.19	-.31	.761	Not significant
Number of Training Attended						
0-2	Ref.	--	--	--	--	--
3-4	-.03	.09	-.11	-.39	.698	Not significant
5-6	.03	.11	.10	.28	.781	Not significant
≥ 7	.10	.11	.33	.98	.332	Not significant
Teaching Position						
Teacher I	Ref.	--	--	--	--	--
Teacher II	-.03	.10	-.11	-.36	.723	Not significant
Teacher III	-.22	.10	-.71	-2.12*	.037	Significant
Master Teacher	.15	.12	.48	1.23	.222	Not significant

Note: R2 = .127 ANOVA for Regression: F=1.05, p=.409 *significant at .05 level

Table 11 explores the relationship between the demographic profile of respondents and their teaching performance. The predictors included gender, age, years of service, number of training attended, and teaching position. The results show that only one predictor, "Teaching Position: Teacher III," is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, with a p-value of 0.037. The regression coefficient for Teacher III is -0.22, indicating a negative relationship with teaching performance. This suggests that compared to Teacher I (the reference category), being in the Teacher III position is associated with a decrease in teaching performance.

Notably, the R-squared value of 0.127 indicates that the model explains approximately 12.7% of the variance in teaching performance, suggesting that the selected predictors collectively have a modest explanatory power. The ANOVA for regression has an F-value of 1.05 with a p-value of 0.409, indicating that the overall model is not statistically significant. This implies that, as a whole, the selected predictors do not significantly contribute to explaining the variation in teaching performance.

Examining individual predictors, gender, age, years of service, number of training attended, and teaching position, the majority are not significant contributors to explaining differences in teaching performance. It is crucial to note that while some predictors may not be statistically significant, they might still have practical significance, and their effects should be interpreted in the context of the specific study.

In summary, the noteworthy result from this regression analysis is the significant negative relationship between being in the "Teacher III" position and teaching performance. This finding can guide further investigations into the factors contributing to this observed relationship and inform targeted interventions to support teachers in this position.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the teaching competencies and the teaching performance of the respondents?

Table 12. Regression Analysis of Relating the Teaching Competencies on the Teaching Performance of the Respondents

Predictor	Regression Coeff.	S.E.	Stand. Coeff.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
(Constant)	3.76	.32	--	11.70	<.001	Significant
Knowledge	.29	.16	.34	1.84	.069	Not significant
Skills	-.007	.17	-.008	-.04	.967	Not significant
Attitudes	-.21	.11	-.26	-1.84	.069	Not significant

Note: R2 = .066 ANOVA for Regression: F=2.27, p=.086 not significant at .05 level

Table 12 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between teaching competencies (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) and teaching performance. Note that the predictors (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) individually do not exhibit statistical significance in relation to teaching performance.

The regression coefficients for knowledge, skills, and attitudes are 0.29, -0.007, and -0.21, respectively. While the coefficient for knowledge shows a positive relationship with teaching performance (albeit not statistically significant at the 0.05 level), skills and attitudes exhibit negative relationships. However, none of these individual predictor coefficients reach statistical significance, as evidenced by their respective p-values (0.069 for Knowledge and Attitudes, and 0.967 for Skills).

The R-squared value of 0.066 indicates that the model explains about 6.6% of the variance in teaching performance, suggesting a limited explanatory power of the selected predictors. Additionally, the ANOVA for Regression has an F-value of 2.27 with a p-value of 0.086, indicating that the overall model is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Thus, none of the individual predictors (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) demonstrate a significant relationship with teaching performance. This implies that, based on this analysis, teaching competencies, as measured in this study, may not be strong predictors of teaching performance.

Problem 6: What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Proposed Title: "Teaching Enhancement Workshops: Empowering Educators for Excellence"

Rationale:

The proposed title, "Teaching Enhancement Workshops: Empowering Educators for Excellence," reflects the comprehensive nature of the action plan designed to uplift teaching performance and foster continuous improvement among educators. "Teaching Enhancement Workshop" highlights the central goal of enhancing teaching practices, while "Empowering Educators for Excellence" communicates the overarching aim of empowering teachers to excel in their roles.

The use of "Empowering" underscores the plan's commitment to providing teachers with the tools, knowledge, and support needed to elevate their teaching performance. The term "Excellence" reflects the aspiration for a high standard of teaching that goes beyond mere satisfaction, aiming for outstanding educational outcomes. Then, the proposed title conveys a sense of purpose and empowerment, aligning with the action plan's objectives to improve teaching performance, strengthen teaching competencies, and cultivate a culture of continuous improvement among educators.

Date: January 2024

Vision: To improve teaching performance, strengthen teaching competencies, and cultivate a culture of continuous improvement among educators.

Key Action Steps/Strategies to Achieve Objective	Persons Responsible	Resources/Budget Needed	Date of Completion	Threats/Potential Barriers	Indicators of Success
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Conduct workshops and seminars for "Teacher III" position teachers on effective teaching strategies and classroom management.	School Head Professional Development Coordinator. Teachers	Funding for professional development workshops.	Jan 2024	Teachers often have busy schedules with numerous responsibilities, making it challenging for them to allocate time for additional workshops and seminars	100% of the participants understood the topics being discussed.
Develop and deliver training modules addressing knowledge, skills, and attitudes in teaching.	.School Head Professional Development Coordinator. Teachers	Training materials and resources.	Feb. 2024	Some teachers may resist adopting new teaching methods or technologies, hindering the successful implementation of training modules.	100% of the participants understood the topics being discussed.
Facilitate regular peer-to-peer learning sessions and collaborative lesson	School Head Professional Development Coordinator. Teachers	Time allocated during regular school hours for collaborative activities.	March 2024	Teachers may perceive that they don't have enough time to engage in peer-to-peer learning or collaborative lessons. The existing curriculum and schedule may be tight, making it challenging to allocate time for additional activities.	100 % of the participants improved teamwork and collaboration are evident, as participants work together more efficiently and effectively.

Conclusion

This study concluded that the evaluation of teachers' competencies and performance offers a favorable perspective on the overall educational landscape. The robust competencies demonstrated in knowledge, skills, and attitudes underscore a commitment to effective teaching practices, fostering a student-centered learning environment. The emphasis on real-life examples, effective communication, and continuous professional development reflects a dynamic teaching approach that contributes to a positive and engaging educational atmosphere.

The IPCRF ratings further validate the effectiveness of the teaching staff, with a majority falling within the very satisfactory range. The absence of extreme ratings suggests a consistent and balanced level of teaching quality, highlighting the overall competence of the educators. However, the identification of teaching position, particularly the negative association of Teacher III with teaching performance, underscores the need for targeted support and interventions in specific roles. The complex relationship between teaching competencies (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) and performance, with limited explanatory power, highlights the multifaceted nature of factors influencing teaching effectiveness. These findings collectively underscore the importance of continuous assessment, targeted support, and a holistic understanding of the dynamics at play in enhancing teaching practices within the specific educational context

For school administrators, these findings underscore the importance of tailored professional development initiatives that take into account the diverse competencies and challenges associated with different teaching positions. Targeted support programs for educators in roles like Teacher III, identified as having a significant negative association with teaching performance, could prove instrumental in addressing specific needs and fostering improvement. Moreover, administrators should encourage a collaborative and inclusive approach to professional development, ensuring that the positive aspects highlighted, such as effective communication and continuous professional growth, are shared and celebrated across the teaching staff.

Teachers should consider these results as an opportunity for self-reflection and continued professional growth. Engaging in ongoing training, particularly in areas where skills-related competencies may be perceived as needing improvement, can contribute to sustained effectiveness in the classroom.

For learners, the positive teaching competencies identified in this study affirm the commitment of educators to providing a quality learning experience. However, learners can actively contribute to their own educational journey by expressing their needs and preferences in the learning process. Open communication channels between teachers and students can facilitate a more responsive and tailored educational experience that aligns with the strengths and interests of the learners. Future researchers should build upon these findings by delving deeper into the specific factors that contribute to teaching effectiveness, especially in diverse teaching positions. Exploring the dynamics of professional development, teacher collaboration, and the impact of teaching competencies on student outcomes could provide valuable insights. Adopting a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative analysis with qualitative exploration could offer a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of teaching effectiveness within the educational context under study.

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